

Atypical Manifestation of Syphilis

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Written patient consent for academic publication of the photograph was obtained and is held by the authors

A 32-year-old heterosexual male, engaging in sexual risk behaviors, presented to the emergency department with a painful lesion in the sacrococcygeal region. Initially diagnosed as a pilonidal abscess, it was drained, but the condition showed poor evolution. Subsequent referral to the coloproctology clinic revealed a lesion with irregular edges, nodular characteristics, and a central crater; a biopsy confirmed the presence of *Treponema pallidum*. The patient was referred to the infectious disease team and started treatment with Benzathine Penicillin. Its capacity to mimic other dermatological conditions and deviate from typical clinical patterns, result in delays to achieve an appropriate treatment.

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